

ONLINE PHARMACY PRODUCTS STORE

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Abstract. The Online Pharmacy Products Store project is not only to be convenience the pharmaceutical companies but also to serve a wider audience of pharmacies and people related to the world of medicine field. The purpose of writing this project is for customers in any location to be well-known about our company's product names more and to be able to order them whenever they need, and to inform our medicine products' updated information such as price changes at any time. The website was developed using modern web development technologies, including HTML, CSS, JS, PHP and MySQL to improve both customer satisfaction and products management.

Keywords: HTML, CSS, Bootstrap, Javascript, PHP, MySQL

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital world, having an effective online pharmacy products store is crucial for providing a smooth shopping experience and easy management. This project aims to create a reliable platform where customers can easily find and buy pharmaceutical products, while administrators can manage the store efficiently. The goal is to make shopping for medicines convenient for customers and store management simple for the staff. By using modern technology and design, the Pharmacy Products Store will improve customer satisfaction and help the business grow.

PROBLEM

Traditional pharmacies often face challenges such as limited hours, geographical constraints, and restricted inventory. Customers may find it inconvenient to visit physical stores, especially in cases of urgency or when searching for specific products that may not be readily available. For business owners, managing orders, inventory, and customer service can be labor-intensive and inefficient. This highlighted the need for a more accessible and efficient solution for both customers and administrators.

APPROACH

The project developed an online pharmacy store to make shopping more convenient for customers and to simplify management for owners. The store allows customers to easily search for products, view available stock in real-time, and purchase items directly from the website. For store owners, an admin panel is provided to manage products, orders, and

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deliveries quickly. The technologies used include Bootstrap for mobile-friendly design, jQuery for interactive features, and PHP/MySQL for secure data management.

Customers can register or log in to their accounts, browse product categories, view product details, and add items to their shopping cart. They can also change the quantity of products before checkout. Admins can access their dashboard to add, update, or remove products, manage categories, and process customer orders. The platform also supports safe payment options such as Kpay, WavePay, and cash on delivery.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. The ER (Entity-Relationship) diagram for the user and admin side of the Online Pharmacy Products Store system represents the various entities involved and their relationships. Users, Admins, Products, Categories, Cart and Orders key entries are included in figure 2.

Figure 2: Database Design

RESULTS

Once the system is developed, it is crucial to move on to system testing to ensure there are no bugs and that the software functions as intended. During this phase, developers must promptly fix any bugs or errors that are found, as early resolution of issues prevents more problems that are significant later. Testing involves evaluating the software for differences between the actual output and what is expected, identifying discrepancies that may compromise system quality. This step is vital for both validation and verification, ensuring that the software meets all specified requirements and performs correctly. System testing isn't confined to the development team; it also includes feedback from external users, whose fresh perspectives may reveal overlooked issues. This collaborative approach ensures that the system meets all requirements, functions properly in real-world scenarios, and enhances user experience. The following figure 3 illustrates the system's implementation, showing the various components and their interactions.

Search Product

Search

Clear

Category

Marketed By: YE ZH LATT Co., Ltd.

Amcan-5
3100 mmk

Marketed By: YE ZH LATT Co., Ltd.

Amimol
5900 mmk

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Window

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The pharmacy products store project has effectively delivered a user-friendly platform that simplifies the process of finding and purchasing medicines. Key features, including detailed product views, an intuitive checkout process, and efficient order management, enhance the overall shopping experience. By using modern design and technology, the platform has improved accessibility and convenience for users. Looking ahead, there are opportunities to further enhance the shop by incorporating personalized recommendations, expanding mobile functionality, and integrating additional features to better meet customer needs and stay competitive in the market.

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